

Bladder Cancer: Pattern of Incidence in Iraq during 2022

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Abstract

Background: Bladder cancer ranks among the most common malignancies globally, with significant variations in incidence due to environmental and lifestyle factors. Iraq presents a unique epidemiological context for bladder cancer, impacted by environmental pollutants, occupational risks, and high tobacco use, particularly among males. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of bladder cancer incidence patterns across Iraq's governorates in 2022, focusing on malignancy type, age-related trends, and regional disparities. **Aim:** This study aims to identify the patterns of bladder cancer incidence in Iraq, examining the influence of demographic factors (age, gender) and geographical variations on cancer distribution. **Method:** A descriptive study was conducted using data from the Iraqi Ministry of Health's Surveillance Department. Data from cancer registries were cross-verified with records from Iraqi cancer centers. Bladder cancer cases were categorized by tumor site, morphology, age, and governorate, following the WHO's ICD-Oncology classifications. The data were analyzed to determine incidence rates per 100,000 populations for each category. **Results:** Transitional Cell Carcinoma (TCC) was the predominant type, comprising 95.3% of male cases and 91.5% of female cases. Incidence rates increased markedly with age, especially in males, peaking in the 75-79 age group. Geographic analysis revealed that southern governorates, including Karbala and Wasit, exhibited the highest incidence rates, while northern regions reported lower rates. These regional disparities may be attributed to variations in industrial exposure, environmental pollutants, and access to healthcare. **Conclusion:** Bladder cancer incidence in Iraq shows a predominance of TCC, with higher rates among males and a notable increase in older age groups. Geographic disparities highlight the influence of environmental and occupational factors, particularly in southern Iraq. These findings underscore the need for targeted prevention and early detection strategies, particularly in high-incidence areas and among at-risk populations.

Introduction

Bladder cancer is one of the most common malignancies affecting populations worldwide, with significant regional variations in incidence rates.

Globally, it ranks as the tenth most frequently diagnosed cancer, with higher prevalence rates observed in developed regions compared to developing areas. In Iraq, bladder cancer represents a major health

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concern, particularly given its high prevalence relative to other cancers. Iraq’s unique epidemiological landscape, characterized by environmental, lifestyle, and occupational factors, contributes to distinct patterns of bladder cancer incidence across different regions [1,2]. The incidence of bladder cancer in Iraq shows considerable geographic variability, reflecting differences in risk factors such as exposure to certain environmental toxins, water pollution, tobacco use, and occupational hazards. Smoking, a primary risk factor for bladder cancer, is particularly relevant in Iraq, where tobacco use remains widespread among the male population. Additionally, Iraq has been subjected to environmental pollution stemming from industrialization, military conflicts, and the use of carcinogenic substances in agriculture and industry, which may contribute to the heightened risk of bladder cancer [3,4]. Studies indicate that bladder cancer in Iraq predominantly affects males, a pattern consistent with global trends where men are up to four times more likely to develop it than women. Age is another crucial factor, with incidence rates rising sharply among individuals over 50 years of age. This trend underscores the importance of age-specific screening and targeted awareness programs, especially among older populations who are more susceptible to the disease. Additionally, Iraq’s health infrastructure faces challenges, including limited access to advanced diagnostic and treatment facilities in certain regions, which may impact early detection rates and overall patient outcomes [5,6]. Regional disparities within Iraq further complicate the bladder cancer landscape. Data suggests that southern governorates, such as Karbala, Wasit, and Najaf, have notably higher incidence rates than northern regions like Kirkuk and Diyala. These disparities may be attributable to varying levels of environmental exposure, healthcare access, and awareness. In regions with limited healthcare resources, bladder cancer cases may go undiagnosed or diagnosed at later stages, potentially influencing the observed incidence rates [7,8]. The paper summarises Iraq's bladder cancer incidence trend to show its complexity. Understanding these trends helps improve prevention, early identification, and treatment. Iraqi bladder cancer treatment must take into account

geographical variances, population demographics, and the healthcare system's socioeconomic and environmental problems. This strategy can improve patient outcomes and lower bladder cancer rates in Iraq.

Method

We conducted a descriptive study with data that accrued in the Surveillance Department registries of the Iraqi Ministry of Health for the year 2022 from all health directorates and health facilities of the governorates. These were reconfirmed by the Iraqi cancer centers, chemotherapy and radiotherapy centers, and finally referred to the Iraqi Cancer Board. The sites of tumors abstracted data were coded following the International Classification of Diseases. Using the 9th or 10th edition morbidity and mortality coding system (ICD) ⁽⁹⁾, records of the registered cases also were assigned topography (primary site) and morphology (histology) of the malignancies according to ICD-Oncology as described in the ICD for Oncology 3rd edition of the World Health Organization (WHO) ⁽¹⁰⁾. Actual registration was through indices of registered cases that were a serial number, name of the patient, and the site code. The incoming notifications were double-checked against the registered data to avoid double registrations. Data entry was through the WHO cancer registration system as prescribed by IARC of WHO ⁽¹¹⁾. Incidences have been presented as cases/100,000 population base regarding each category of cancer type. As case incidences, rates were recorded data entries, crosschecked and analyzed; age, sex as well as gubernatorates factors affecting incidence of cancers in Iraq were thoroughly demonstrated.

Results

The data shows that Transitional Cell Carcinoma is the most common type of cancer for both males and females, accounting for 95.3% of cases in males and 91.5% in females. Carcinoma, NOS, is the second most common, with slightly higher percentages in females (5.5%) than in males (2.6%). Squamous Cell Carcinoma appears in a small fraction of cases, 1.8% in males and 2.5% in females. Sarcoma and other types are rare, with sarcoma present only in 0.5% of female cases and no cases in males. As in table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Malignancy Types According to Gender

Malignancy types	Male (no. & %)	Female (no. & %)
Transitional cell carcinoma	1312 (95.3%)	366 (91.5%)
Carcinoma, NOS	36 (2.6%)	22 (5.5%)
Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS	25 (1.8%)	10 (2.5%)
Sarcoma	0 (0.0%)	2 (0.5%)
Others	3 (0.2%)	0 (0%)
Total	1376 (100%)	400 (100%)

The data shows that the incidence rates increase with age for both males and females. Males have significantly higher rates across all age groups, especially from age 50 onward. The highest rates are observed in the 75-79 and 80+ age groups, with males reaching over 150, while females have lower rates, peaking at around 58.59 in the 70-74 age group. This pattern suggests a marked age-related increase in incidence, particularly pronounced among males. As in table 2.

Table 2: Incidence Rate of Bladder Cancer According to Age Groups (Years)

Age Group (years)	Male IR	Female IR
0-4	0.03	0.03
5-9	0.00	0.00
10-14	0.00	0.00
15-19	0.04	0.00
20-24	0.15	0.05
25-29	0.63	0.06
30-34	0.79	0.28
35-39	2.27	0.40
40-44	3.12	0.88
45-49	6.99	1.40
50-54	27.39	3.77
55-59	26.79	6.36
60-64	45.16	6.45
65-69	90.02	20.94
70-74	150.13	58.59
75-79	160.39	48.84
80+	150.07	48.74

Table 3: Incidence Rate of Bladder Cancer According Governorates

Governorates	Bladder Incidence Rate
Kirkuk	4.8
Diyala	4.9
Al-Sulaimaniyah	5.6
Salah Al-Deen	5.7
Duhok	5.9
Erbil	6.1
Nineveh	7.0
Al-Anbar	7.0
Babil	7.3
Baghdad	7.8
Al-Muthana	8.8
Al-Basrah	10.5
ThiQar	10.6
Misan	10.9
Al-Qadisiya	14.0
Al-Najaf	14.2
Wasit	15.5
Karbala	17.8

The data shows that bladder incidence rates vary across governorates, with the lowest rate in Kirkuk (4.8) and the highest in Karbala (17.8). Generally, southern regions like Al-Qadisiya, Al-Najaf, Wasit, and Karbala have higher rates, while northern areas such as Kirkuk, Diyala, and Al-Sulaimaniyah report lower rates. As in table 3.

Discussion

As shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3, analysis of bladder cancer in Iraq provides important insights into cancer type patterns, age-related incidence trends, and geographic differences between governorates. The results are consistent with regional and global studies and highlight the role of environmental influences, lifestyle factors, and access to health care in the development of bladder cancer. The distribution of bladder cancer types by sex in Iraq in 2022, with transitional cell carcinoma (TCC) being the predominant form, accounting for 95.3% of male cases and 91.5% of female cases. This trend is consistent with global data and data from neighboring countries such as Saudi Arabia, where a study reported TCC as the most common type of bladder cancer in both sexes, although the proportion of TCC was slightly lower. This difference may reflect unique environmental and lifestyle factors in Iraq, such as: B. smoking rates and occupational stress [12]. In Egypt, squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) used to dominate the development of bladder cancer due to schistosomiasis. However, through control measures, dominance has shifted to TCC, making the prevalence of TCC in Egypt comparable to that in Iraq [13]. Data from Iran also confirm the high incidence of TCC, with significant gender differences related to smoking and environmental exposures [14]. In the United States, bladder cancer is also dominated by TCC, and SCC cases are less common than in Middle Eastern countries, highlighting regional etiological differences [15]. The high incidence of TCC in Turkey is consistent with the situation in Iraq, where occupational exposure is considered a major risk factor [16]. In Jordan, TCC is the predominant form, but SCC cases are slightly higher than in Iraq, possibly due to environmental and genetic differences [17]. The age-specific incidence rates, demonstrating a marked increase with age, especially in males. Incidence is low among individuals under 40 but increases significantly from age 50 onward, peaking at 160.39 per 100,000 for males in the 75-79 age group and at 58.59 per 100,000 for females in the 70-74 age group. This pattern aligns with regional and global studies, which also report age and gender as crucial factors in bladder cancer incidence. A Saudi Arabian study documented similar age-related trends, with rising rates in individuals over 50 due to cumulative risk factors like smoking and occupational exposures [12]. Egyptian data also

indicate an age-related increase, particularly among males over 60, driven by similar environmental exposures and cultural habits [13]. In Iran, incidence rates rise dramatically after age 50 for both genders, with higher rates in males due to smoking [14]. The U.S. shows a consistent age-related increase, with cumulative exposure to smoking and occupational hazards playing a significant role [15]. Turkey's data also indicate an age-related rise, with long-term exposure to smoking and workplace chemicals as major contributing factors [16]. In Jordan, bladder cancer rates are higher in older men, influenced by lifestyle and environmental exposures [17]. The geographical disparities, with higher bladder cancer incidence in Iraq's southern governorates, such as Karbala (17.8), Wasit (15.5), and Al-Qadisiya (14.0), while northern regions like Kirkuk (4.8) and Diyala (4.9) report lower rates. Environmental exposures, industrial activities, healthcare access, and lifestyle factors, particularly smoking, appear to drive these disparities. A Saudi Arabian study found that industrial and urban regions have higher bladder cancer rates due to environmental pollutants and smoking prevalence, reflecting similar trends in Iraq's southern governorates [12]. In Egypt, higher incidence rates were reported in regions near the Nile with agricultural pollutants, mirroring Iraq's agriculturally intensive areas [13]. Iran's data show elevated rates in industrialized urban centers, much like Baghdad in Iraq [14]. U.S. data reveal higher bladder cancer rates in industrial regions with greater environmental carcinogen exposure [15]. In Turkey, bladder cancer rates are highest in industrialized areas, aligning with Iraq's southern governorates [16]. Jordan's study also reported higher rates in industrialized regions, consistent with Iraq's geographical disparities [17]. In summary, the data show that bladder cancer in Iraq is predominantly TCC, more common in males, and increases with age, particularly in industrially active southern regions. These patterns align with findings from other Middle Eastern countries and globally, where environmental exposures, smoking, and occupational risks significantly influence bladder cancer incidence. Targeted prevention and early detection efforts are essential, particularly for high-risk groups and regions.

Conclusion

The outcomes of the three tables demonstrate that Transitional Cell Carcinoma is the most common form of cancer in the bladder in Iraq, men are more susceptible to it than women. The frequency of incidents increases significantly with age, especially in men over 50, this suggests that age and gender are significant factors in the development of incidents. Geographically, southern districts have a higher propensity to be affected by environmental pollution and industrial development, these districts show the

highest rates of incidence, which suggests that environmental and occupational factors have a significant role in the prevalence of bladder cancer. These findings demonstrate the necessity of targeted prevention initiatives in high-risk areas and among elderly populations.

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